

FOSTERING ORGANIZATIONAL BEHAVIOR THROUGH ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT & HR EMPOWERMENT: PSYCHOLOGICAL CONTRACTS AS A MEDIATION

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of organizational support and HR empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior mediated by employee's psychological contracts at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV (Persero) Medan. This study used a quantitative approach in its analysis. A questionnaire as a primary data collection tool from 126 research samples taken proportionally randomly from a population of 389 employees at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV (Persero) Medan. Path analysis is used as the data analysis technique. It is found that organizational support and HR empowerment have a significant effect on employees' psychology contracts. Psychological contracts act as a significant mediator variable in the intermediate effect of organizational support and HR empowerment. The direct influence between organizational support and HR empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior is greater through the direct path than the indirect. This research focuses on organizational antecedents simultaneously, namely organizational support and HR empowerment, and their effect on organizational citizenship behavior through the psychological contract. There is still very limited specific study of HR empowerment activities on the psychological contract of workers. This study contributes to the existing literature on the soft aspects of human resources than the physical aspect. To increase high organizational citizenship behavior, it is necessary to instill a psychological contract in employees through the facilitation of organizational support and HR empowerment which is even better in various forms, including providing variations awards, working conditions, fulfillment of welfare, self-development activities, placement of employees in positions that are under competence, harmonious working relationships.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Organizational support, HR Empowerment, Psychological Contracts, Public Sector

1 INTRODUCTION

Human resources in organizations are required to keep pace with technological developments by improving the quality of work and extra-role behavior that supports organizational effectiveness. Extra-role behavior is known as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (hereinafter referred to as OCB) (Podsakoff et al., 2006),

namely discretionary behavior that is explicitly recognized by the formal system. OCB describes a form of prosocial behavior for organizations consisting of positive, constructive, and meaningful social behavior to help. Someone who has a high level of OCB will have loyalty and devotion to the organization (Nooralizad et al., 2011), work productivity (Jin-Liang & Hai-Zhen, 2012; MacKenzie et al., 1993), individual performance (Basu et al., 2017; Chandra et al., 2020; Wijaya, 2020), organizational performance (Podsakoff & MacKenzie, 2009), service quality (Djati, 2009), customer satisfaction and decreased turnover (Emami et al., 2012), capital formation social (Basu et al., 2017). Even based on research findings it turns out that the presence of OCB in employees can lead to various unwanted consequences for individuals, groups, and organizations including work stress, overload, and work-family conflict (Bolino et al., 2016), in general OCB contributes positively both individuals and the organization as a whole. In an organization that has a task and environmental complexity, extra-role behavior is needed besides of course behavior within the role in carrying out various work activities.

OCB certainly appears out of nowhere. Various antecedents trigger the emergence of OCB in workers both individually and organizationally, including commitment, motivation, employee morale (Djati, 2009; Junita et al., 2022), organizational justice, role clarity, individual nature, organizational commitment (Emami et al., 2012), self-interest, prosocial motives (Michel, 2017), positive affectivity (Hayati & Caniango, 2021), emotional intelligence, organizational support (Junita et al., 2022), servant leadership style, employee empowerment, and superior-subordinate interaction (Sari et al., 2021).

This research focuses on organizational antecedents, namely organizational support and HR empowerment. Focus on how these two factors have a direct impact on the growth of workers' psychological attachment to the organization, and indirectly on the emergence of OCB. Workers who have a strong psychological contract with the organization are thought to be empirically more likely to manifest OCB work behavior than workers without a psychological contract. Existing research so far examines HR practices in general in generating psychological contracts (Katou, 2013; Kong, 2020; Nassar, 2021; Scheel et al., 2013). There is still very limited specific study of HR empowerment activities on the psychological contract of workers. This aspect is the significance of this research.

Organizational support is an employee's perception of various forms of support provided by the organization as a form of organizational concern for the welfare of employees. Employees who perceive that organizational support is high will have a high organizational identity and then develop more positive relationships and perceptions of the organization. Theoretical and empirical studies state that when employees feel fully supported by the organization, psychological ties to the organization will grow (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; Pricelia & Handoyo, 2015; Son, 2014.; Sun, 2019). The existence of a psychological contract among workers will impact their extra-role behavior (OCB) (Aledeinat & Alrfou, 2017; Azhar et al., 2019; Varma & Chavan, 2020).

It is believed that HR empowerment can also be used as a means to foster psychological bonds between employees and the organization. Employee empowerment is giving authority to employees to plan, control, and make decisions about the work they are responsible for, without having to obtain explicit authorization from the leadership above them. HR empowerment is a worker empowerment activity identified as a way of increasing OCB (Antoni & Sujatha, 2017; Eskandari & Dadashkarimi, 2017; Fadhal et al., 2021; Hartono, 2019; Jufrizen et al., 2019; Sari et al., 2021; Sukadar & Priyono, 2015).

Organizational support is an employee's perception of everything that is provided by the organization to employees to support work effectiveness. Organizational support is an important aspect of the organization because it can increase employee OCB behavior based on psychological bonds. The better the employee's perception of organizational support, the stronger the feeling of attachment to the organization will appear which will then manifest in extra-role work behavior (OCB). Theoretical and empirical studies state that when employees feel fully supported by the organization, psychological ties to the organization will grow (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; Pricelia & Handoyo, 2015; Son, 2014; Sun, 2019). In addition to creating psychological bonds, good organizational support will also have significant implications for the emergence of OCB behavior (Alshaabani et al., 2021; Firmansyah et al., 2022; Sakarina et al., 2022).

Psychological contracts have a profound impact on work attitudes and behavior. The existence of a psychological contract will create mutual respect, self-confidence, and the expression of employees who have a high psychological contract with the organization, among others, in the form of extra-role behavior in carrying out work activities every day, commonly referred to as OCB. The existence of a psychological contract among workers will impact their extra-role behavior (OCB) (Aledeinat & Alrfou, 2017; Azhar et al., 2019; Varma & Chavan, 2020).

In addition to organizational support, HR empowerment is identified as a means to grow workers'

psychological ties to the organization. Employee empowerment is giving authority to employees to plan, control, and make decisions about the work they are responsible for, without having to obtain explicit authorization from the leadership above them. HR empowerment is one of the prerequisites for forming employee psychological ties to the organization (Paul et al., 2000; Akram et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2019). Through HR empowerment, employees will optimally complete their tasks. The employee's contribution will exceed the demands of the employee's role at the place of work. HR empowerment is a worker empowerment activity identified as a way of increasing OCB (Antoni & Sujatha, 2017; Eskandari & Dadashkarimi, 2017; Fadhal et al., 2021; Hartono, 2019; Jufrizen et al., 2019; Sari et al., 2021; Sukadar & Priyono, 2015).

These variables were specifically observed at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV (Persero) Medan. The phenomenon that occurs in the company is that the achievement of employee performance targets is still fluctuating. Achievement of work targets is the output of in-role and extra-role work behavior (OCB). It is suspected that the character of OCB behavior that appears is driven by organizational support and HR empowerment conditioned by the company which then has an impact on the psychological contract and OCB (Figure 1).

Based on these theoretical and empirical studies, the hypothesis statement is stated as follows:

H₁: Organizational support and HR empowerment significantly influence the emergence of employee psychological contracts.

H₂: Organizational support and HR empowerment significantly influence Organizational Citizenship Behavior through employee psychological contracts.

Figure 1. Research Framework

2 METHODOLOGY

This research is a causality research that uses a quantitative approach to solve the problem. Research conducted at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV (Persero) Medan. The population as well as the research sample is employees at PT. Perkebunan Nusantara IV (Persero) Medan with a total of 389 employees as a population and 126 employees as a sample. Determination of the number of samples refers to the opinion of (Hair et al., 2019) which was determined based on the number of indicators and variables observed. The sampling technique was carried out using a proportional random sampling technique (Sugiyono, 2018). The primary research data was collected by distributing questionnaires. Of the 126 questionnaires that were distributed by the researcher to the respondents, only 111 questionnaires were returned, and after sorting 104 questionnaires were worth analyzing.

Measurement of research variables is done with a Likert scale (interval). Organizational support variables are measured by 4 indicators proposed by (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002) including reward systems, self-development opportunities, working conditions, and employee welfare. The HR empowerment variable is measured by 7 indicators proposed by (Mangkunegara, 2013) which include conformity of responsibilities with employee competence, suitability of work with employee expertise, the accuracy of decisions made by employees, management's trust in employees, close working relationship between management and employees, and accuracy of employee development. The psychological contract variable is measured by 4 indicators proposed by Pervin et al. (2010) which include shared obligations, belief in promises, agreement with the organization, and mutual expectations. The OCB variable is measured by 7 indicators proposed by Podsakoff et al. (2006) including sportsmanship, civic virtue, helping behavior, organizational loyalty, organizational compliance, individual initiative, and personal development. The data analysis technique used inferential statistical path analysis (Sarwono, 2007). Path analysis was used to analyze the direct and

indirect effects between independent and dependent variables.

3 FINDINGS

3.1 Respondents' Characteristics

The characteristics of research respondents can be explained based on gender, education level, and length of work. The majority of respondents were male, 68 respondents (65.38%), 64 respondents (61.54%) reached the final level of undergraduate education, and 35 respondents (33.65%) had worked in the company for 4 years.

3.2. The Results of Validity and Reliability Tests

Validity and reliability tests are used to measure the quality of the research instrument, namely the question items on the questionnaire. Instrument validity was tested by looking at the correlation value between the question item scores and the total score through the Corrected-Item Total Correlation value with a cutoff value of 0.30 (Ghozali, 2016). The reliability test was carried out by looking at the Cronbach Alpha value for each variable with a cutoff value of 0.60 (Ghozali, 2016). From the results of testing the validity and reliability of the research instruments, it is known that all the questions stated are valid and reliable.

3.3. The Classic Assumption Test Results

Hypothesis 1 wants to test the effect of organizational support and HR empowerment on psychological contracts. Before testing the research model of hypothesis 1, a classic assumption test was first carried out on the model which consisted of normality, multicollinearity, and heteroscedasticity tests. The results of the normality test by using The Kolmogorov Smirnov's test show the significance value (Asymp. Sig. 2 - tailed) of 0.6538 so that a significance value of $0.086 > 0.05$. It means that the data is normally distributed. Based on the heteroscedasticity test, it is known that the significant value of the organizational support variable (X_1) is 0.982 and the HR empowerment variable (X_2) is 0.328, which means it is greater than 0.05. Then, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the model of hypothesis 1. The results of the multicollinearity test show the value of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for variable X_1 is 3.319, and variable X_2 is 3.319. Each independent variable has a value of less than 10. Likewise, the Tolerance value for the X_1 variable is 0.301 and the X_2 variable is 0.378. From each variable, the tolerance value is greater than 0.1 so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity symptom in each variable.

Then hypothesis 2, namely the effect of organizational support and HR empowerment on organizational citizenship behavior through psychological contracts. Before testing hypothesis 2, a classic assumption test was first carried out on the research model which consisted of the normality test, test, and heteroscedasticity test. The results of the normality test by using The Kolmogorov Smirnov's test show the significance value (Asymp. Sig. 2 - tailed) of 0.170 so that a significance value of $0.170 > 0.05$. It means that the data is normally distributed. Based on the heteroscedasticity test, it is known that the significant value of the organizational support variable (X_1) is 0.156, the HR empowerment variable (X_2) is 0.966, and the psychological contract (Z) is 0.370 which means it is greater than 0.05. Then, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity in the hypothesis 2 model. The results of the multicollinearity test show the value of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) for variable X_1 is 3.550, variable X_2 is 5.023, and variable Z is 3.985. Each independent variable has a value of less than 10. Likewise, the Tolerance value for the X_1 variable is 0.282, the X_2 variable is 0.199, and the Z variable is 0.251. From each variable the tolerance value is greater than 0.1 so it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity symptom in each variable.

3.4. The Hypothesis Test Results

The contribution of organizational support and HR empowerment variables to psychological contracts can be seen in the results of the F-test and the t-test (Table 1). Hypothesis model 1 is considered to fit with real facts in the field regarding the contribution of organizational support and HR empowerment to workers' psychological contracts. Based on Table 1, it is known that the significant value of the organizational support variable (X_1) is $0.009 < 0.050$, and the significant value of the HR empowerment variable (X_2) is $0.000 < 0.050$. Thus it can be concluded that organizational support and HR empowerment have a significant effect on psychological contracts.

Table 1. The Result of Hypothesis 1 Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	F	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	-2.105	2.142		-.983	.328	150.727	.000
	X1	.290	.109	.241	2.652	.009		
	X2	.519	.072	.654	7.202	.000		

a. Dependent Variable: Z

The results of the hypothesis 2's goodness of fit with the F test found a model significance value of 0.000 < 0.050 as shown in Table 2. Thus it is concluded that organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) through a psychological contract (Z). In other words, hypothesis 2 is accepted. Changes in the psychological contract were determined by variations in changes in organizational support and HR empowerment of 87.1%, the rest were influenced by various other variables not observed in this study.

Table 2. The Result of Hypothesis 2 Test

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	F	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
1	(Constant)	2.583	.947		2.728	.008	231.960	.000
	X1	.156	.050	.209	3.132	.002		
	X2	.265	.039	.541	6.813	.000		
	Z	.145	.044	.234	3.306	.001		

a. Dependent Variable: Y

The contribution of organizational support and HR empowerment variables to psychological contracts can be seen in the results of the t-test (Table 2). Based on Table 2, it is known that the significant value of the organizational support variable (X_1) is 0.002 < 0.050, the significant value of the HR empowerment variable (X_2) is 0.000 < 0.050, and the significance value of the psychological contract variable (Z) is 0.001 < 0.050. Thus it can be concluded that organizational support and HR empowerment have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through psychological contracts.

Figure 2. Results of Path Analysis of Sub Structure I and II

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test, it can be described that the research path analysis framework includes sub-structure paths 1 and 2 equipped with the values of the results of data processing (Figure 2). According to Ghazali (2001) for each dependent variable (endogenous variable), there will be an arrow pointing to this variable and this serves to explain the amount of unexplained variance by that variable. To calculate the value of e^2 , you can use the following formula:

$$e = \sqrt{(1-R^2)}$$

$$R^2 = \text{Determination Coefficient}$$

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test, it is known that the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a significant effect both directly on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) and indirectly through the psychological contract variable (Z). To find out which one has the greater influence, whether directly or indirectly, it is necessary to do a calculation as shown in Table 3. Based on Table 3, it appears that the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a greater direct influence on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) than indirectly, namely through the psychological contract variable (Z). However, the psychological contract variable is capable of being a mediating variable in this study.

Table 3. The Calculation of Direct Indirect Influence Exogenous to Endogenous Variables

Substructure	Path Coefficients			Total Effect
	Pathway	Direct	Non-Direct	
Substructure I	$X_1 \rightarrow Z$	0,241	-	0,241
	$X_2 \rightarrow Z$	0,654	-	0,654
	$X_1 \rightarrow Y$	0,209	$0,241 \times 0,234 = 0,056$	$0,209 + 0,056 = 0,265$
Substructure II	$X_2 \rightarrow Y$	0,541	$0,654 \times 0,234 = 0,153$	$0,541 + 0,153 = 0,694$
	$Z \rightarrow Y$	0,234	-	0,234

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

4.1. The Effect of Organizational Support and HR Empowerment on Psychological Contracts

Organizational support is believed to be an important aspect of the organization that can increase employee extra-role behavior (known as the concept of Organizational Citizenship Behavior). Employees who feel cared for and valued will feel comfortable and grow a strong psychological bond with the organization. The employee will then be willing to contribute extra energy at work. Theoretical and empirical studies state that when employees feel fully supported by the organization, psychological ties to the organization will grow (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; Pricelia & Handoyo, 2015; Son, 2014.; Sun, 2019).

On the other hand, the conditioning of employee empowerment in work organizations is also important. Employee empowerment is the granting of authority to employees to plan, control, and make decisions about the work they are responsible for without having to obtain explicit authorization from the leadership. Employee empowerment means involving employees optimally in completing their duties. It is also believed that HR empowerment can also be used as a means to foster psychological bonds between employees and the organization. HR empowerment is one of the prerequisites for forming employee psychological ties to the organization (Paul et al., 2000; Akram et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2019).

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test, it is known that the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a significant effect directly on organizational citizenship behavior (Y). The contribution of HR empowerment to workers' organizational citizenship behavior is greater than organizational support (Table 2). Management's attention to indicators such as conformity of responsibilities

with employee competence, suitability of work with employee expertise, the accuracy of decisions made by employees, management's trust in employees, close working relationship between management and employees, and accuracy of employee development is of importance which is higher than the physical aspects of the organization. Thus the results of this study are in line with the results of previous research (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003; Pricelia & Handoyo, 2015; Son, 2014; Sun, 2019) which stated that organizational support is an important aspect of organizations because increase employee OCB behavior based on psychological bonds. Likewise, research findings related to the effect of HR empowerment on OCB (Antoni & Sujatha, 2017; Eskandari & Dadashkarimi, 2017; Fadhal et al., 2021; Hartono, 2019; Jufrizen et al., 2020; Sari et al., 2021; Sukadar & Priyono, 2015) which proves that HR empowerment is a way of increasing employee OCB.

4.2. The Effect of Organizational Support and HR Empowerment on Organizational Citizenship Behavior through Employee Psychological Contracts

Everything in the organization can become the object of employee perception, which will then influence their attitudes and work behavior. The existence of organizational support and HR empowerment which is well perceived by employees will have implications for various things. The better the employee's perception of organizational support, the stronger the feeling of attachment to the organization will appear which will then manifest in extra-role work behavior (OCB). HR empowerment is a worker empowerment activity identified as a way of increasing OCB (Antoni & Sujatha, 2017; Eskandari & Dadashkarimi, 2017; Fadhal et al., 2021; Hartono, 2019; Jufrizen et al., 2019; Francis & Narayanan, 2020; Sari et al., 2021; Sukadar & Priyono, 2015).

The existence of organizational support and HR empowerment which is well-perceived by employees will also foster a strong psychological contract. Psychological contracts don't just appear out of nowhere. The psychological contract arises because of the employee's belief that the organization has good faith in meeting the various expectations held by employees (Moorhead & Griffin, 2013). Implicitly, a strong psychological contract includes a positive assessment of employees for all forms of support conditioned by the organization. Therefore the psychological contract is closely related to aspects of employee attitudes and behavior. Research proves that the existence of positive attitude aspects within oneself will have a very strong impact on the emergence of positive work behavior including Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Junita, 2016; Abun et al., 2021; Ds & Haider, 2021; Cabrera & Estacio, 2022). A strong psychological contract in employees will have a significant impact on extra-role behavior (Organizational Citizenship Behavior), namely the willingness of employees to contribute more to the organization beyond the description of their main duties (Aledeinat & Alrfou, 2017; Azhar et al., 2019; Varma & Chavan, 2020).

Based on the results of the research hypothesis test, it is known that the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a significant effect on the psychological contract variable (Z). The contribution of HR empowerment to workers' psychological contracts is greater than organizational support (Table 2). As well as the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a significant effect indirectly on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) through the psychological contract variable (Z). The psychological contract variable is capable of being a mediating variable in this study. However, it appears that the organizational support (X_1) and HR empowerment (X_2) variables have a greater direct influence on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) than indirectly, namely through the psychological contract variable (Z). The existence of a psychological contract also has an important impact in bringing out positive work attitudes and behavior of employees. The existence of a psychological contract will create mutual respect, confidence, and employee expression towards the organization, among others, in the form of extra-role behavior in carrying out work activities every day which is commonly referred to as OCB. The existence of a psychological contract among workers will impact their higher extra-role behavior (OCB) on employees (Aledeinat & Alrfou, 2017; Azhar et al., 2019; Varma & Chavan, 2020).

5. CONCLUSION

The research findings answer the formulation of the problem as well as the research hypothesis that (1) organizational support and HR empowerment have a significant effect on psychological contracts; (2) organizational support and HR empowerment have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through a psychological contract. To increase high organizational citizenship behavior, it is necessary to instill a psychological contract in employees through the facilitation of organizational support and HR empowerment which is even better in various forms, including providing variations awards, working conditions, fulfillment of welfare, self-development activities, placement of employees in positions that are under competence, harmonious working relationships.

This research has limitations in the number of research samples and data collection techniques in the form

of questionnaires which allow bias to occur in perceiving the questions asked by researchers, as well as an explanation of the relationship between a variety of other variables that are capable of creating a psychological contract and positive work behavior of employees other than what has been observed in this study.

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